

Spider diversity in a native grassland fragment in Irene, in the Gauteng Province, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: Interest in the invertebrate faunas of urban and suburban areas has increased in the last few years. Over a period of six years, spiders were regularly collected and photographed in a native grassland patch near Irene in the Gauteng Province, South Africa. It is home to a diverse group of spiders, and 39 spider families represented by 150 genera and 257 species have been collected. The Araneidae (46) Salticidae (36 spp.), and Thomisidae (32 spp.) are the most species-rich families. Several of the species collected are new to science or first records for Gauteng. All species collected have been photographed, and this has added a valuable contribution to the South African National Survey of Arachnida Virtual Museum and iNaturalist. It is important that pristine areas like this in urban areas be protected and not developed.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation assessment, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The increasing growth of the urban population is one of the main challenges of this century. The role of cities in the loss and degradation of global biodiversity was already recognised at the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) in 1992. Whilst cities pose major challenges for protecting biodiversity, the opportunities they offer to protect invertebrate biodiversity have largely been ignored. These areas, although fragmented, can serve an important ecological function and require proper management and conservation. Interest in the invertebrate faunas of urban and suburban areas has increased in the last 10-15 years, especially in Europe and North America (Bolger *et al.*, 2000; Frazer & Frankie, 1986).

In South Africa, only a handful of urban surveys have been carried out since the end of the last century. Most of these surveys were undertaken in national gardens and small reserves within the boundaries of cities. Tucker (1920) was the first to report on the spiders of the Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden in the Western Cape. Follow-up surveys in the Western Cape were mainly undertaken on the Table Mountain (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024) and Kirstenbosch (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). Clark & Samways (1997) studied arthropods, including spiders, in a botanic garden in Pietermaritzburg, KwaZulu-Natal and spiders from road islands in Durban (Whitmore *et al.*, 2002). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), surveys were undertaken throughout the country. In the Free State, surveys were undertaken in the Free State National Botanical Garden (Butler & Haddad, 2011; Neethling & Haddad, 2013). From Gauteng, a three-year survey at the Rietondale Research Station in Pretoria was reported on by Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991). Also from Pretoria, there are checklists of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022a), the Groenkloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023) and the Pretoria National Botanical Garden (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024).

The only survey in a home garden was undertaken in the Eastern Cape at Jeffreys Bay, where 151 species were recorded (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023). We report here on the Irene Grassland Survey (IGS) carried out in the pristine grassland fragment near the Irene Village, Centurion, in the Gauteng Province of South Africa (Figs 1-3). The province falls within both the Savanna and the highly threatened Grassland Biome, and approximately 83% of the province comprises Highveld Grassland vegetation types, of which a mere 0.8% is currently conserved in South Africa.

We present a comprehensive checklist of spiders sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey (IGS) and include information on the species' global distribution, endemism, and conservation status.

Figures 1–3. The native grassland fragment sampled in Irene in the Gauteng Province, South Africa during the Irene Grassland Survey. Credits: Peter Webb.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The second author (PW) first visited this small, pristine grassland area bordering Irene in 2013 and sampled numerous interesting invertebrates. He decided to survey the area on a regular basis as part of SANSa Grassland surveys and it was known as the Irene Grassland Survey (IGS). Although it was not conceived as a scientific study as such, the result of observations and sampling undertaken over a six-year period resulted in several new records and 257 spider species sampled.

Study area: The small hectare pristine grassland area of the small village of Irene (25° 53'29.81" S 28°14'04.62" E) in Centurion, South Africa, is approximately 1 km² in size at an altitude of 1465 m a.s.l. (Fig. 4). The western boundary appears to be a little disturbed with alien weed and houses on its border (Figs 1-2, 4). The area is burnt on an annual basis, usually around July.

The area is on dolomite and is a haven for many different species of grass with an abundance of wildflowers in the spring. Although trees are sparse, the odd Buffalo thorn (*Ziziphus mucronata*), white stinkwood (*Celtis africana*), dogwood (*Rhamnus prinoides*), karee, taaibos, and *Grewia flava* make it very typical of Highveld grassland (Fig. 3). The following grasses have been recognised: Heart-seed love grass (*Eragrostis capensis*); Natal Red-Tops (*Melinis repens*); Common Finger Grass (*Digitaria eriantha*); Velvet Signal Grass (*Brachiaria serrata*); Red Grass (*Themeda triandra*), and Hairy trident Grass (*Tristachya leucothrix*) (Figs 1–3, 5–8).

Study period and methods: This checklist is the result of spider collecting carried out using different techniques over different time periods. Most of the collecting was by hand but also included occasional use of sweep netting and pitfall traps. The arachnids were identified by the first author (ASD). Voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria.

Photography: The spiders were photographed, some in the field and others in a studio in Irene using a Nikon D200 camera body with a Nikon 105mm macro lens coupled with an R1 wireless flash kit by PW. The photographs could be viewed on the iNaturalist dataset.

Conservation status: The conservation status of each species was derived from a recent National Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020), where spatial analysis on observed occurrences using functions for Extent of Occurrence (EOO), Area of Occupancy (AOO), and elevational range of the area of occupation was determined. The assumed knowledge of the full range for all species based on their observed occurrences, and EOO was calculated as the minimum convex polygon around all occurrences, and the 2 km² cells occupied were used to calculate AOO. The distribution of threats across lineages was visualized using a mosaic plot, with the size of rectangles representing the proportion of species in a specific family represented within the categories: Data Deficient (DD) and Least Concern (LC) (Table 3).

TABLE 1. Results of four Gauteng Urban Area Survey project of SANSa undertaken in Pretoria urban areas, listing the total number of families and species and the three most species rich families recorded.

LOCALITY	SPP.	FAM	ABUNDANT FAMILIES			REFERENCES
FAERIE GLEN NATURE RESERVE	103	31	Salticidae (17)	Araneidae (12)	Thomisidae (11)	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022e
GROENKLOOF NATURE RESERVE	112	35	Salticidae (20)	Gnaphosidae (12)	Lycosidae (11)	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2023
IRENE GRASSLAND	257	39	Araneidae (46)	Salticidae (36)	Thomisidae (32)	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb
PRETORIA NATIONAL BOT. GARDEN	152	36	Araneidae (23)	Salticidae (21)	Thomisidae (14)	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2024

Figure 4. The yellow block show the area sampled in Irene.

Figures 5–8. Showing the field type and the different grass species sampled during the Irene Grassland survey. Credit: Peter Webb

Endemicity value: The global distribution of each species obtained from literature and the World Spider Catalog was provided to determine the endemicity value of each species (Table 3). Values used to indicate species endemicity (E): 6 – only known from the type locality (Irene); 5 – known from several localities in the Gauteng (GE); 4 – known from Gauteng as well as an adjacent province; 3 – known from more than two provinces in South Africa (SAE); 2 – known from other Southern African countries (STHE); 1 – known from other countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE); 0 – also from countries outside the Afrotropical Region (CE).

RESULTS

Numbers present: A total of 257 species, 152 genera, from 39 families, were recorded (Tables 2 & 4). The IGS formed part of the Gauteng Urban Area Survey project of SANSA in Pretoria, where several surveys have been undertaken (Table 1). The first survey dealt with the spider diversity of the Faerie Glen Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022e), where 103 species were recorded, followed by 112 species from the Groenkloof Nature Reserve and 152 species from the Pretoria National Botanical Garden. The 257 van Irene is 100 species more than the Groenkloof survey. This could be attributed to the longer sampling period in Irene. Owen (2010) emphasized the importance of ongoing long-term monitoring when assessing the diversity of even small areas, particularly for invertebrates whose populations often exhibit significant inter-seasonal and inter-annual fluctuations.

TABLE 2: Spider diversity of the Irene Grassland Survey, Gauteng with the total number of families, genera (G) and species (SPP.) sampled

FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	%	FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	%
Agelenidae	3	3	1.2	Philodromidae	5	9	3.5
Araneidae	22	46	17.9	Pholcidae	3	3	1.2
Cheiracanthiidae	1	3	1.2	Phyxelididae	1	1	0.4
Clubionidae	1	2	0.8	Pisauridae	3	5	1.9
Corinnidae	4	4	1.6	Prodidomidae	2	3	1.3
Cyrtacheniiidae	1	3	1.2	Salticidae	21	36	14.
Deinopidae	1	1	0.4	Scytodidae	1	2	0.8
Dictynidae	1	1	0.4	Segestriidae	1	1	0.4
Eresidae	1	1	0.4	Selenopidae	1	2	0.8
Gnaphosidae	17	21	8.2	Sparassidae	2	2	0.8
Hersiliidae	1	1	0.4	Stasimopidae	1	1	0.4
Idiopidae	1	3	1.3	Tetragnathidae	1	3	1.3
Linyphiidae	3	3	1.3	Theraphosidae	1	1	0.4
Liocranidae	1	1	0.4	Theridiidae	9	14	5.8
Lycosidae	10	18	7.0	Thomisidae	12	32	12.5
Macrobunidae	1	1	0.4	Trachelidae	4	4	1.6
Oecobiidae	1	1	0.4	Trochenteriidae	1	1	0.4
Oonopidae	1	1	0.4	Uloboridae	2	2	0.8
Oxyopidae	3	13	5.1	Zodariidae	5	5	1.9
Palpimanidae	1	2	0.8	39 families	152	257	

Family diversity: Of the 39 spider families collected (Tables 2 & 5), the three most species-rich families are the Araneidae (46 spp.), Salticidae (36 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (32 spp.). Thirteen families are represented by singletons.

The Salticidae, with 36 species, was the family with the highest number of species recorded from the four surveys in Pretoria, with the number ranges between 17 and 36 species (Table 1). All the Salticidae species of Irene were identified to species level and they are all listed as Least Concern (Table 5).

The Araneidae was the most species-rich family in two of the Pretoria sites, with numbers ranging between 23 and 46 (Table 1). Several interesting Araneidae species have been recorded from Irene. Six species that could not be identified to species level are possibly new records for South Africa (Figs 9a-f), and five species were first records from South Africa and 12 first records for Gauteng (Table 3; Figs 10a-d; 11-14).

Figure 9 (a-f). Some of the undetermined Araneidae species recorded from Irene.

Figure 10 (a-d). Araneidae species from Irene recorded for the first time from South Africa and Gauteng.

The Thomisidae was the third species-rich family recorded from the three Pretoria sites, with numbers ranging from 11 to 32 species as recorded from Irene (Table 1). All the thomisids were identified to species level and they are all listed as Least Concern (Table 5).

Specimens sampled during this 6-year survey were regularly photographed and more than a 1000 photographs became available. With series of photographs on species available we were able to publish several papers on new records and the behaviour of species such as *Ammoxenus* (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2024a (Fig. 26) and *Hogna* spp. (Fig. 27). Specimens also form part of generic revisions (Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013 (Table 3; Figs 18 & 19).

TABLE 3: Spider species sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey that were first records for Gauteng and South Africa.

SPECIES	FIRST RECORD	REFERENCE
ARANEIDAE		
<i>Araneus coccinella</i> Pocock, 1898	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2020 (Fig. 10a)
<i>Argiope tapinobata</i> Bjørn, 1997	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022a (Fig. 11)
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2021 (Fig. 10b)
<i>Isoxya mossamedensis</i> Benoit, 1962	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022a (Fig. 10c)
<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022b (Fig. 16)
<i>Neoscona kivuensis</i> Grasshoff, 1986	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022b (Fig. 17)
<i>Ursa turbinata</i> Simon, 1895	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022c (Fig. 10d)
CORINNIIDAE		
<i>Apochinomma elongata</i> Haddad, 2013	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2022 (Fig. 12)
LYCOSIDAE		
<i>Pardosa schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , (Fig. 19)
<i>Zenonina albocaudata</i> Lawrence, 1952	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , (Fig. 20)
MACROBUNIDAE		
<i>Elelies limpopo</i> Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022 f (Fig. 13)
THERIDIIDAE		
<i>Latrodectus pallidus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1872	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2022d (Fig. 14)
THOMISIDAE		
<i>Heriaeus copricola</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2020a (Fig. 18)
<i>Heriaeus peterwebbi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	South Africa	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> 2020a (Fig. 19)
<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> , 2020b (Fig. 22)
<i>Synema marlothi</i> Dahl, 1907	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (Fig. 23)
<i>Synema simoneae</i> Lessert, 1919	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (Fig. 24)
TETRAGNATHIDAE		
<i>Leucauge auronotum</i> Strand, 1907	Gauteng	Dippenaar-Schoeman <i>et al.</i> (Fig. 25)

TABLE 4: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey, Gauteng.

CONSERVATION STATUS	NO. SPP.	%
Not evaluated NE	19	7.4
Data deficient DD	3	1.2
Least concern LC	235	91.4
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	23	8.9
1 – African endemics (AE)	111	43.2
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	50	19.5
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	52	20.2
4 – South African endemics (SAE):	0	0
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)	2	0.8
6 – Type locality	0	0

Argiope tapinobata

Apochinomma elongatum

Elelies limpopo

Latrodectus pallidus

Heliophanus africanus

Figures 11-15. Spider species sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey. For more information on the species see Table 3.

Endemism: Twenty-three species (8.9%) sampled at Irene have a distribution wider than Africa, while 111 species (43.2%) are African endemics (AE), 50 species (20.2%) are Southern African endemics, and 54 species (21%) are South African endemics (Table 4). Only two species was endemic to Gauteng a Stasimopidae trapdoor spider *Stasimopus robertsi* Hewitt, 1910 and a Salticidae *Heliophanus africanus* Wesotowska, 1986 (Fig. 15).

Conservation status: Nineteen species were not evaluated and two species: *Nemoscolus obscurus* Simon, 1897, *Cheiracanthium dippenaarae* Lotz, 2007 were listed as Data Deficient. The rest of the 235 species have a wide distribution with no known threats and are listed as Least Concern (Table 5).

DISCUSSION

Descriptive studies in the United Kingdom suggest that gardens, both urban and otherwise, can harbour a considerable diversity of spider species (Dawson, 2003; Gurr, 1968; Russell-Smith, 2002a; Thomas, 2002; , Owen, 2010). Numbers of species recorded in the 10 gardens included in these reports ranged from 23 to 113, representing from 3% to 17% of the British spider fauna.

Gauteng, the smallest of South Africa's nine provinces, is rich in biodiversity. During SANSA surveys 461 spider species have been recorded (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). The 257 species recorded from IGS represent 55.7% of the Gauteng fauna. Yet it is also the most densely populated province and thus faces significant development pressures. It is the most densely populated province in the country with the highest population growth rate and the demand for urban land in this rapidly urbanizing province is therefore high.

CONCLUSION

From these surveys, it has become clear that gaps in our knowledge of the grasslands of Gauteng still exist, especially regarding the urban and suburban areas (Haddad *et al.*, 2013). Although Gauteng is the smallest province in South Africa, it is characterized by high biodiversity. Consequently, the biodiversity in the province is highly threatened by industrialization, mining, agriculture, and especially urbanization, the latter due to the current high demands for the provision of land and basic services to alleviate poor living conditions. Essentially, the successful conservation of biodiversity within Gauteng will require the identification of priority areas where development habitat transformation and fragmentation should be discouraged and conservation efforts should be focused.

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Nemoscolus cotti

Neoscona kivuensis

Heriaeus copricola

Heriaeus peterwebbi

Pardosa schreineri

Zenonina albocaudata

Synema decens

Synema marlothi

Synema simoneae

Leucauge auronotum

Ammoxenus amphalodes

Hogna spenceri

Oxyopes sp. (undetermined)

Oxyopes sp. (undetermined)

Figures 16-28. Spider species sampled during the Irene Grassland Survey. For more information on the species see Table 3

TABLE 5: Spiders of Irene Grassland Survey listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEND) LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated, EN Endangered.

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
1. AGELENIDAE				3. CHEIRACANTHIIDAE			
<i>Agelena</i> sp. 1		NE		<i>Cheiracanthium africanum</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	<i>Cheiracanthium dippenaarae</i> Lotz, 2007	3	DD	SAE
<i>Olorunia punctata</i> Lehtinen, 1967	1	LC	AE	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
2. ARANEIDAE				4. CLUBIONIDAE			
<i>Araneus</i> sp. 1 (Fig. 9a)		NE		<i>Clubiona africana</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
<i>Araneus coccinella</i> Pocock, 1898	3	LC	SAE	<i>Clubiona pupillaris</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	5. CORINNIDAE			
<i>Argiope lobata</i> (Pallas, 1772)	0	LC	C	<i>Apochinomma elongata</i> Haddad, 2013	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE
<i>Argiope tapinobata</i> Björn, 1997	1	LC	AE	<i>Merenius alberti</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Caerostris sexcuspudata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	<i>Messapus martini</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	6. CYRTAUCHENIIDAE			
<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ancylotrypa brevivalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	<i>Ancylotrypa nigriceps</i> (Purcell, 1902)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C	<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C. L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	7. DEINOPIDAE			
<i>Hypsosinga pygmaea</i> (Sundevall, 1831)	1	LC	AE	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
<i>Hypsosinga</i> sp. 2 (new) (Fig. 9b)		NE		8. DICTYNIDAE			
<i>Hypsosinga</i> sp. 3 (new) (Fig. 9c)		NE		<i>Archaedictyna conducta</i> (O.P.- Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	9. ERESIDAE			
<i>Isoxya mossamedensis</i> Benoit, 1962	2	LC	STHE	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
<i>Isoxya mucronata</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE	10. GNAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	<i>Ammoxenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
<i>Larinia chloris</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	<i>Aphantaulax inornata</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Larinioides</i> sp. (undetermined) (Fig. 9f)		NE		<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Lipocrea longissima</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE	<i>Drassodes bechuanicus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus elongatus</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Nemoscolus obscurus</i> Simon, 1897	3	DD	SAE	<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Nemoscolus vigintipunctatus</i> Simon, 1897	2	LC	STHE	<i>Megamyrmaekion transvaalense</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Nemoscolus</i> sp. (new) (Fig. 9d)		NE		<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
<i>Neoscona kivuensis</i> Grasshoff, 1986	1	LC	AE	<i>Smionia lineatipes</i> (Purcell, 1908)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE	<i>Trephopoda kannemeyeri</i> (Tucker, 1923)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Neoscona penicillipes</i> (Karsch, 1879)	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus aurariarum</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona rapta</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE	<i>Xerophaeus biplagiatus</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
<i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Neoscona vigilans</i> (Blackwall, 1865)	0	LC	C	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
<i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885)	0	LC	C	11. HERSILIIDAE			
<i>Prasonica nigrotaeniata</i> (Simon, 1909)	1	LC	AE	<i>Hersilia sericea</i> Pocock, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	12. IDIOPIDAE			
<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE	<i>Idiops fryi</i> (Purcell, 1903)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Ursa turbinata</i> Simon, 1895	3	LC	SAE	<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Ursa</i> sp. 2 (new) (Fig. 9e)		NE					

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
13. LINYPHIIDAE				22. PHOLCIDAE			
<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE	<i>Thanatus dorsilineatus</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
<i>Limoneta sirimoni</i> (Bosmans, 1979)	2	LC	AE	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE	<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
14. LIOCRANIDAE				<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Rhaeboctesis transvaalensis</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE	<i>Tibitanus sexmaculatus</i> Simon, 1907	1	LC	AE
15. LYCOSIDAE				23. PHYXELIDIDAE			
<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Quamtana hectori</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
<i>Allocosa exserta</i> Roewer, 1959	2	LC	STHE	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE
<i>Amblyothele ecologica</i> Russell-Smith, Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2009	3	LC	SAE	<i>Spermophora</i> sp. (immature)		NE	
<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	24. PISAURIDAE			
<i>Foveosa adunca</i> Russell-Smith, Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	SAE	<i>Afropisaura ducis</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE
<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE	<i>Afropisaura rothiformis</i> (Strand, 1908)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	<i>Cispus variegatus</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE	<i>Euprostenops bayaonianus</i> (Brito Capello, 1867)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hogna zuluana</i> Roewer, 1959	3	LC	SAE	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	25. PRODIDOMIDAE			
<i>Pardosa schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	<i>Eleleis limpopo</i> Rodrigues & Rheims, 2020	1	LC	AE
<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Theuma elucubata</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Theuma parva</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Proevippa hirsuta</i> (Russell-Smith, 1981)	2	LC	STHE	26. SALTICIDAE			
<i>Proevippa schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Trabea heterocolata</i> Strand, 1913	1	LC	AE	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trabea ornatipalpis</i> Russell-Smith, 1982	3	LC	SAE	<i>Dendryphantes silvestris</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013	3	LC	SAE
<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
<i>Zenonina albocaudata</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE	<i>Evarcha vittula</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
16. MACROBUNIDAE				<i>Festucula leroyae</i> Azarkina & Foord, 2014	2	LC	STHE
<i>Chresiona</i> sp.		NE		<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
17. OECOBIIDAE				<i>Helafricanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C	<i>Helafricanus trepidus</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
18. OONOPIIDAE				<i>Heliocapensis charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE
<i>Gamasomorpha australis</i> Hewitt, 1915	3	LC	SAE	<i>Heliophanus africanus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	5	DD	SAE
19. OXYOPIIDAE				<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE	<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Kima atra</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Helafricanus pistaciae</i> (Wesolowska, 2003)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Myrmarachne marshalli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	<i>Myrmarachne uvira</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes pallidecoloratus</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes schenkeli</i> Lessert, 1917	1	LC	AE	<i>Neaetha bulawayoensis</i> (Wesolowska, 2000)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 3 (green)		NE		<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesolowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 9 (black)		NE		<i>Pellenes modicus</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 10 (velvet)		NE		<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE	<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
20. PALPIMANIDAE				<i>Rhene lingularis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	<i>Rumburak laxus</i> (Zhang & Maddison, 2012)	3	LC	SAE
<i>Palpimanus</i> sp. 2 (immature)		NE		<i>Thyene aperta</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
21. PHILODROMIDAE				<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE				
<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE				
<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE				
<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	1	LC	AE				

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus deamatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Trapezocephalus infaustus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus lesserti</i> (Wesołowska, 1986)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus orchestra</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE
<i>Trapezocephalus transvaalicus</i> (Simon, 1901)	3	LC	SAE
27. SCYTODIDAE			
<i>Scytodes caffra</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Scytodes thoracica</i> (Latreille, 1802)	0	LC	C
28. SEGESTRIIDAE			
<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
29. SELENOPIIDAE			
<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
<i>Anyphops lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
30. SPARASSIDAE			
<i>Eusparassus jaegeri</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE
<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
31. STASIMOPIDAE			
<i>Stasimopus robertsi</i> Hewitt, 1910	5	LC	SAE
32. TETRAGNATHIDAE			
<i>Leucauge argyrescens</i> Benoit, 1978	1	LC	AE
<i>Leucauge auronotum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE
<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
33. THERAPHOSIDAE			
<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
34. THERIDIIDAE			
<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C
<i>Dipoena</i> sp. 1			NE
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus pallidus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1872	0	LC	C
<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE
<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
<i>Steatoda erigoniformis</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	0	LC	C
<i>Theridion piliphilum</i> Strand, 1907			
<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3			NE
<i>Theridion</i> sp. 7			NE
<i>Tidarren</i> sp. 1			NE
35. THOMISIDAE			
<i>Ansiea tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
<i>Heriaeus copricola</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	2	LC	STHE
<i>Heriaeus peterwebbi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	2	LC	STHE
<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
<i>Monaeses fuscus</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1984	3	LC	SAE
<i>Monaeses quadrituberculatus</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE

FAMILIES/SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxytate ribes</i> (Jézéquel, 1964)	1	LC	AE
<i>Pactactes obesus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia depressa</i> Simon, 1906	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	0	LC	C
<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
<i>Synema marlothi</i> Dahl, 1907	2	LC	STHE
<i>Synema simoneae</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus congoensis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus dalmasi</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989	1	LC	AE
<i>Tmarus foliatus</i> Lessert, 1928	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus fagei</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
<i>Xysticus urbensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
36. TRACHELIDAE			
<i>Afroseto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
<i>Orthobula radiata</i> Simon, 1897	1	LC	AE
<i>Poachelas striatus</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	3	LC	SAE
<i>Spinotrachelas</i> sp. (immature)			NE
37. TROCHANTERIIDAE			
<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1887)	1	LC	AE
38. ULOBORIDAE			
<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
39. ZODARIIDAE			
<i>Capheris decorata</i> Simon, 1904	1	LC	AE
<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
<i>Microdiores</i> sp. 1			NE
<i>Ranops robinae</i> Jocqué & Henrard, 2020	3	LC	SAE
<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE